

**WHY DICK AND JANE DON'T ASK:
GETTING PAST INITIATION BARRIERS IN DYADIC NEGOTIATIONS**

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Abstract

Negotiation is an essential skill for personal well-being and professional success, a skill that begins with identifying and acting on one's wants and needs. Individuals, however, often lack the confidence, motivation, or training to simply ask for what they want in many situations. This paper discusses the personal characteristics and situational factors that influence an individual's ability to ask for what he/she wants in a negotiation. Specific suggestions for managing this critical phase of the negotiation process also are offered.

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Negotiation is generally considered one of the essential skills necessary for organizational effectiveness and success (Greenhalgh, 2001; Mintzberg, 1973). Individuals in all types of organizations and at all organizational levels negotiate on a daily basis – staffing requirements, budgets, project deadlines, meeting dates/times, purchases, joint ventures, etc. Many of the negotiating skills of the most effective individuals are employed in both personal and professional negotiations (Cohen, 1980; Lewicki, Barry, & Saunders, 2007).

As with most processes (e.g., problem solving, decision making, group/team development), the early stages of the negotiation process often influence how succeeding stages will unfold (Wheeler, 2004). Figuring out what one wants is part of the challenge in these encounters, as all humans have multiple wants and needs with varying degrees of importance (Gist, Stevens & Baretta, 1991). Yet even when individuals have clear aspirations, they might not ask for what they want (Babcock & Laschever, 2003; Volkema, 1999).

For some individuals, this is a chronic problem. They lack the social skills, confidence, or will to initiate encounters. For others, the behavior is more episodic. In either case, the result is almost certain to be the same – a suboptimal outcome. Why do

individuals fail to ask for what they want in a negotiation, or ask for less than they desire, even in apparently benign situations where the other party is willing to cooperate and the likelihood of a favorable agreement is quite high?

The purpose of this paper is to delineate the reasons why individuals do not ask for what they want in a negotiation, focusing on both the characteristics of individual negotiators and the situational factors that are likely to moderate their thinking in the early stages of a negotiation. Three distinct behaviors can emerge from these intentions, which are reviewed in turn. Finally, specific techniques are discussed for overcoming or countering these tendencies not to pursue one's aspirations or desires.

Understanding the Phenomenon

Negotiation has been defined as a communication between two or more parties regarding the nature of future behavior (Volkema, 1999). While this communication can be verbal or nonverbal, at some point most negotiations involve a verbal exchange. Indeed, many would contend that this is the point at which negotiation truly begins: A request is made from one party to another party regarding future behavior (e.g., an offer to purchase goods or services, a request to alter company policy, etc.).

While not asking for what one wants does not ensure failure in an encounter (silence has its virtues), it often reduces the chances of a successful negotiation (Babcock & Laschever, 2003). Yet despite the fact that many individuals recognize this cause-and-effect relationship, they often choose avoidance and its consequences over initiating the

asking behavior that could result in a satisfactory outcome for all. Why (and how) does this happen?

Understanding why people do not ask for what they want requires an appreciation for the architecture and functionality of the human brain. The human brain is, for all practical purposes, three brains – the brain stem, the limbic system, and the cerebrum (Morse, 2006). The brain stem is the most primal structure, and controls our fundamental survival needs (e.g., food, water, shelter). This structure is common to most animals – reptiles, fish, dogs, cats, etc.

The limbic system is where many emotions are processed, including anger, sorrow, and happiness. The limbic system is sometimes referred to as the “dog brain” because it is a structure found in higher order animals such as dogs. It is the reason why your dog is happy to see you when you come home, but your fish (which only has the equivalent of a brain stem) is not.

The cerebrum separates humans from most other animals, as this is where more complex reasoning occurs. The cerebrum contains cognitive scripts that have been developed over time, and these scripts help guide behavior in specific situations. A situation viewed as “thirst,” for example, can trigger related scripts in memory that instruct an individual on how to act or react (e.g., in a public building, look for a drinking fountain) (O’Connor & Adams, 1999).

Many scripts are formed over years of experience, initially through trial and error.

Eventually, an individual comes to expect a certain outcome in a given situation and acts according to script (Steel & Konig, 2006; Weiss, 1994). Combinations of scripts also are possible, as when a manager is overworked and tired, visualizes asking for a day off, anticipates how her boss will likely respond to the request at such a busy time of year, and imagines how she will feel and react to her boss's denial.

Cognitive scripts, therefore, provide a link between an individual's wants or desires and his/her needs. The former (e.g., a day off) represent a means of satisfying the latter (e.g., being overworked and tired). Because scripts are based on prior experiences, and because they often are enacted subconsciously, individuals can get locked into their wants (positions) and lose sight of their original needs (interests), particularly if the limbic system becomes active (Fisher & Shapiro, 2005; Morse, 2006). As a consequence, other means of satisfying one's broader needs or interests can go unrealized (Fisher, Ury & Patton, 1991).

Scripts, of course, are not immutable, but they generally do not change in an instant (although particularly dramatic, recent experiences can weigh heavily on one's cognition). Therefore, it is important to understand the personal factors associated with scripts and script development, as well as the situational factors that can moderate their use. Each of these factors can potentially influence a negotiator's intentions to take action, which in turn can predict actual behavior (Chang, 1998; Kim & Hunter, 1993) (Figure 1).

Insert Figure 1 about here.

Negotiator Characteristics

In negotiation, “asking” represents a form of verbal assertiveness, one dimension of an individual’s personality found in the dual-concerns model of conflict/negotiation styles (Shell, 2001). There are two factors central to determining assertive behavior – an individual’s attitude towards such behavior, and the individual’s self-efficacy (Bandura, 2001; Huppertz, 2003).

Attitude. The primary source of an individual’s attitude towards “asking” in a negotiation is socialization or culture. Society determines what is considered normal or acceptable behavior, which can cause individuals to hesitate or retreat in certain situations. According to cognitive dissonance theory, an individual will experience the greatest anxiety or dissonance when his/her behavior is: a) counter-normative, b) voluntary, and c) public (Festinger & Carlsmith, 1959).

Anyone who has ever taught a class to a diverse international audience has probably witnessed the affects of culture on classroom participation. Some students will ask questions and offer comments without hesitation, while other students will say little if anything, even when participation is mandated. In many countries (e.g., Taiwan, China), classes follow a strict lecture format: The instructors are there to impart knowledge, and the students are expected to listen quietly. Thus, any active participation on the part of a student could potentially be viewed as adversarial behavior (Liu & Littlewood, 1997).

Similarly, menus, sticker prices, and the like are viewed in some cultures as implicit contracts to be accepted or rejected, while they are but a starting point for negotiations in other cultures (Schuster & Copeland, 1996). That is, in some cultures individuals are socialized to conform to policies, procedures, and rules, whereas in other cultures these rules are seen as more symbolic than deterministic (Hofstede, 1997).

Demographic factors determine who has power and authority in a social encounter or negotiation in some cultures. In Japan, for example, age is revered. An individual is expected to defer to the wisdom of an elder in personal and professional settings (Marsland & Beer, 1983). Consequently, elders are more likely to take the lead in discussions, while younger members listen and follow.

The behavior of men and women also is influenced by socialization and custom. In many Middle Eastern countries, for example, women hold a subservient role in society (Metcalf, 2006). In this role, they are expected to defer to the judgment of their husbands and other males. However, even in Western societies women are less likely to take the initiative in a negotiation. According to Babcock and Laschever (2003), women often are more apprehensive about negotiations than are men, and consequently they are less likely to initiate a negotiation. And when they do negotiate, women generally ask for and receive considerably less than do men (e.g., in salary negotiations).

Much of this is likely due to the role of women as primary caregivers during an offspring's early years. Women are socialized to be nurturing and cooperative (the other

dimension in the dual-concerns model) in most cultures (Babcock & Laschever, 2003; Walters, Stuhlmacher & Meyer, 1998). These qualities suggest a strong concern for the other party or relationship, which means sacrificing one's own well-being at times for the benefit of another individual. Recent research on men and women acting as agents tends to support this conclusion, as women were found to be less assertive than men when representing themselves, but as assertive when acting on someone else's behalf (Bowles, Babcock & McGinn, 2005).

Socialization, of course, is just a form of collective script development, which can occur in many venues. Individuals are first and foremost socialized to behave in a particular manner through their immediate families, but socialization also occurs in schools, churches, neighborhoods, and communities. It is in these venues that individuals are first taught when and how to initiate negotiations.

Self-efficacy. The other primary negotiator characteristic that can affect initiating behavior is self-efficacy, the belief that one is capable of performing in a certain manner or attaining certain goals. In general, self-efficacy is a function of four factors: personal experience, vicarious experience, social persuasions, and physiological factors (Bandura, 2001).

Since negotiation is a skill, it can be acquired through personal experience or practice. Similarly, confidence and proficiency in asking for what one wants in a negotiation can improve with experience. Individuals become more comfortable with their

behavior through repetition, as well as with the responses they might expect from their counterparts. In their study of negotiation scripts and experience, O'Connor and Adams (1999) found that novice negotiators often assumed that the negotiating parties' interests were incompatible. This, of course, can lead to a belief that the negotiation will be difficult and the outcome distributive (win-lose).

Experience can occur in many different venues, personal and professional. For most of us, the former are much more common than the latter, although we may not recognize that deciding with a friend what movie to see, where to eat, who will drive, what time we will go, and who will pay as negotiations. Since these are communications between two or more parties regarding the nature of future behavior, however, they constitute experience that can determine script development. And some of these scripts can serve to guide behavior in other settings as well (e.g., business negotiations).

Individuals also can become more confident in asking for what they want through vicarious experience (i.e., observing the behavior of skilled others). There are a variety of nuances to asking that can be modeled and learned, from labeling behaviors to the use of open-ended questions. Nadler, Thompson, and Van Boven (2003), in fact, examined four models of knowledge acquisition employed in teaching negotiation skills – didactic learning, experiential learning, analogical learning, and observational learning – and found that observational learning and analogical training were the most effective methods for transferring knowledge and skills.

Social persuasion, a third factor that influences self-efficacy, refers to the support from colleagues and other confederates. This includes encouragement and positive predictions regarding a behavior and its consequences, as well as shaping behavior through the praise and positive reinforcement of early attempts that fail to achieve full expectation but represent developmental progress.

Research on encouragement suggests a significant link between positive reinforcement and performance (London, Larsen & Thisted, 1999), as well as between social support and the lowering of an individual's anxiety and stress (Bluen & Jubiler-Lurie, 1990).

Finally, there are physiological factors that can affect self-efficacy. These factors, which include fatigue, aches and pains, trembling, perspiration, stuttering, and nausea, may not be so easily controlled (Bluen & Jubiler-Lurie, 1990; Wheeler, 2004). Furthermore, a negotiator might fear that the outward appearance of these factors will influence a counterpart's response, which can further accentuate the risks of asking in a negotiation.

Most if not all humans experience at least some of these physiological factors from time to time. In many cases, the symptoms quickly disappear once a behavior is enacted (e.g., engaging a counterpart). But getting past the initial fear can be a serious obstacle for some negotiators, as the limbic system can limit one's ability to act in a deliberate manner (i.e., limiting recall of more effective scripts).

Situational Factors

The relationship between an individual's personal characteristics and his/her intentions to initiate a request is moderated by several situational or contextual factors, including the individual's clarity of purpose or desire, the importance of that desire, time constraints, perceived alternatives, counterpart, and venue or setting.

Clarity of desire. A negotiator's sense of purpose or desire is a response to internal (e.g., hunger) or external (e.g., threat, opportunity) stimuli. We are, in fact, almost constantly bombarded with stimuli, most of which are handled through subconscious processes (Dijksterhuis, 2004). When arousal meets some threshold of urgency, a negotiator will offer conscious attention to the stimulus (Bruner & Pomazal, 1988; Cowan, 1986). This attention includes an attempt to clarify what need must be satisfied, and through what means (wants, desires).

It is not uncommon for a negotiator to lack internal clarity on what he/she wants or needs, which can impede initiation (Volkema, 1999). Most purchases, such as the purchase of an automobile, refrigerator, or copy machine, involve multiple desires on the part of the buyer – price, color, style, delivery date, accessories, warranty. When a party is unclear about his/her priorities, he/she may either forget to pursue some issues or be reluctant to do so. The more issues that come into play, the more likely the individual is to lack clarity (Volkema, 2006).

Importance. Presuming clarity of desire, the importance of one's preferred outcome is a second factor that can moderate initiation behavior (Huppertz, 2003). Importance, of

course, is a relative concept. What is important to one individual may not be important to another individual, and this importance must be determined in relation to other wants and needs. Is the item or issue in question important enough, for example, to risk other issues being brought to the surface during the negotiation?

If a negotiation is important enough, most individuals are willing to take some risks (Volkema & Fleury, 2002). If it is not, they will be more likely to either abstain from raising a sensitive issue or avoid confronting the other party altogether. Those basic needs controlled by the brain stem, needs that are essential to human survival (i.e., food, water, shelter), are likely to be the most potent in determining such risk-taking behavior.

Time constraints. Time is a third situational factor that can moderate the link between negotiator characteristics and intentions. A negotiator can feel harried due to any number of factors, including market conditions (e.g., being a buyer in a seller's market), workload, and externally imposed deadlines.

When negotiators are forced to make a quick decision, they will often be less motivated to process information, be less likely to revise unfounded distributive perceptions, and have a greater likelihood of using stereotypes (de Dreu, 2003). Time constraints also can cause negotiators to re-evaluate what is questionable or inappropriate behavior, increasing their likelihood of acting unethically (Volkema & Fleury, 2002).

In effect, time pressure triggers the limbic system of the human brain. This, in turn, can limit the effectiveness of the cerebrum in analyzing and responding to a situation

logically or creatively (e.g., seeing ways in which a request can be initiated that will lead to a win-win outcome).

Alternatives. The availability of alternatives also can affect the asking process. Generally speaking, having a BATNA (Best Alternative to a Negotiated Agreement) is one of the most effective tools in negotiating (Fisher, et al., 1991; Volkema, 2006). In one study of BATNAs, Brett, Pinkley, and Jackorsky (1996) found that individuals with alternatives had higher outcomes than did individuals without alternatives. Furthermore, they found that the combination of alternatives along with self-efficacy or goal clarity resulted in higher gains as well as a greater probability of reaching an impasse.

Alternatives can take two forms – accepting the status quo, or identifying another party/option (e.g., another business partner). If resigned to the former, a negotiator can still engage his/her counterpart without initiating a request, which leaves open the possibility of the counterpart broaching the subject and making an offer. This reduces a negotiator's anxiety or dissonance, since the introduction of his/her want or need was not volunteered (Festinger & Carlsmith, 1959). The latter – identifying another party – will likely have more potency in determining a negotiator's will to ask, particularly if the alternative(s) involve more familiar or favorable negotiating partners.

Counterpart. A negotiator's perceptions of his/her negotiating counterpart also are taken into consideration when contemplating engagement (Wu & Laws, 2003). Generally, these perceptions relate to the power or leverage of the counterpart. Leverage is based on

perceived wants/needs and alternatives: If the other party has exactly what you want/need and no one else can supply the same, this party has leverage.

Counterparts who appear to be unapproachable (e.g., in an elevated position, behind a partition, projecting an aloof or dismissive attitude) or who display the obvious trappings of success (e.g., large office, expensive furnishings) are often assumed to have little or no interest in what the less powerful have to offer and/or to have alternatives to dealing with any single individual (Volkema, 1999, 2006). In such situations, a series of scripts are often enacted subconsciously, generally leading to a decision not to engage this individual. This can take the form of rationalizing the need for what the other party might offer (i.e., deciding that it is not essential), or exaggerating the availability of one's options.

A counterpart, of course, can seem unapproachable for any number of other reasons. These might include his/her reputation, observable behavior, or native language (which the negotiator might not speak well).

Venue. Finally, venue also can influence a negotiator's intentions to initiate a request. Recall that cognitive dissonance is greatest when an individual's actions are: a) counter-normative, b) voluntary, and c) public (Festinger & Carlsmith, 1959). For a negotiator in an unfamiliar or foreign environment, what is considered counter-normative behavior may not be immediately obvious. For example, is it counter-normative to request that a lawyer be present at an initial meeting? In some countries (e.g., Pacific Rim) this could be viewed as inappropriate (Schuster & Copeland, 1996). Consequently, this

individual may be hesitant to “ask” for fear of violating local sensibilities or customs.

The presence of others also can create anxiety. Most individuals are going to have the greatest difficulty asking for what they want when the negotiating venue is highly public, for fear of being embarrassed in the presence of others if their request is denied. In some cases, individuals will employ third-parties (mediators, agents) to present their case, as a means of avoiding direct contact altogether (Rubin & Sander, 1988).

Intentions and Behavior

Personal characteristics moderated by situational factors will determine an individual’s intentions to “ask” and his/her actual behavior. Reluctance to ask for what one wants can take several forms, including: a) not engaging the other party, b) engaging the other party but not asking for what one wants, and c) engaging the other party but asking for less than what is really desired (Figure 1). The first of these behaviors is, of course, the most severe. By avoiding the other party, one is almost assured that the specific want or need will not be satisfied.

Engaging the other party but not asking for what one wants at least leaves open the possibility that the other party will anticipate one’s desires, or be able to read one’s nonverbal cues and provide a prompt. As previously noted, one of the elements that determines cognitive dissonance is whether or not one’s behavior is voluntary. When one’s counterpart provides a prompt of some type, this reduces the dissonance of voluntarily asking. Therefore, the probability of asking should increase when prompting

occurs.

A third possible behavior involves sub-optimizing one's request. While many negotiators recognize that an exaggerated offer or demand is generally-accepted behavior in most cultures (Dees & Cramton, 1991), some negotiators will ask for less than they actually desire. For example, instead of asking for 100 hours of complimentary internet service, which is preferred, the individual asks for 50 hours of free service. It is possible that such a request will lead to the other party offering what is actually desired (100 hours), but the other party is probably more likely to counter with a lower offer (25 hours).

Buelens and Van Poucke (2004) sought to identify the factors that influence an individual's initial offer in a buyer-seller negotiation. They found that knowledge of a counterpart's alternatives was the best predictor of an initial offer, followed by fairness (based on estimated market value). Thus, if a negotiator believes that a counterpart has alternatives to a negotiated agreement, he/she will be more likely to reduce his/her initial demands.

Presuming that most negotiators would prefer a more desirable outcome (without the loss of respect or face), how can the aforementioned personal characteristics and situational factors be most effectively managed? There are several suggestions that might be offered, some requiring more developmental work than others.

Managing the Initiation Process

There are several points at which specific steps can be taken to increase the

probability of one “asking” in a negotiation, as well as the likelihood of getting a positive response. These include: a) prior to engaging the other party, b) at the moment of initial engagement, and c) when the other party offers his/her decision (yes or no) (Table 1).

Insert Table 1 about here.

Pre-engagement

Pre-engagement begins with clarifying in one’s own mind what one wants, and prioritizing those wants or desires. Equally important is to understand why those issues or desires are important. That is, what need or interest do they serve? By understanding the broader need, one can develop a rationale for the request as well as identify other means (alternatives) of satisfying that interest (Fisher, et al., 1991; Volkema, 1999, 2006).

There may be no factor more effective in easing the challenge of initiating a negotiation than having an alternative (Brett, et al., 1996; Fisher, et al., 1991; Kim & Fragale, 2005). When one knows that being denied a request simply means moving on to the next option, then asking for what one wants is less imposing. Therefore, a negotiator is advised to identify one or more alternatives to a negotiated agreement prior to engaging the other party.

There is always the possibility, of course, that one can exaggerate the availability or desirability of another alternative, using this as a rationale for not initiating a specific

negotiation. Other factors (e.g., urgency, relative value) are likely to influence this cognitive process.

Prior to engaging the other party, a negotiator is also well advised to assess the venue where the negotiation is to take place. As previously noted, public venues are likely to create more dissonance, particularly for the novice negotiator. Therefore, an individual is generally wise to pick a location where the other party has few if any confederates present and where there are no bystanders present. Even a negotiator's own friends and colleagues, when unaware of the negotiator's intended behavior, can complicate the initiation process.

The negotiator might also seek to maneuver the other party to a location that will be perceived as neutral if not favorable. This means, for example, trying to get one's counterpart to move from behind a large desk or partition, or from an elevated position, to a more equitable location. In those cases where the negotiator is seeking a future encounter/negotiation, consider a restaurant, hotel lobby, or one's own office.

Since time constraints can add pressure to the situation, the negotiator should consider picking a time that works to his/her benefit. Generally, this means ensuring enough time to pursue the encounter beyond an initial request (in the event that the other party responds negatively). Again, this can be complicated by the presence of confederates, who might have their own time constraints.

It is generally recommended that a negotiator give some forethought to how a

counterpart might respond to the initial request and rationale, and to plan accordingly. The more compelling one's rationale, the greater the perceived likelihood of a counterpart's acceptance (which may be even more difficult to overcome if one's logic is rejected). Therefore, the more that contingency plans can be developed ahead of time, the less awkward and challenging the exchange is likely to be (Cares & Miskel, 2007; D'Aveni, 2002; Fowler & Layer, 2008).

Finally, if the negotiation is important enough, the novice negotiator should consider rehearsing his/her initial behavior and contingency plan with a more experienced colleague. This is a way of developing new routines (i.e., to overcome any unwanted cognitive scripts that might emerge during the heat of the negotiation). Practice or rehearsing is recommended for many different types of negotiations, including sales (Davidson & Kline, 1999; Gist, et al., 1991, Washburn, 1992), downsizing (Molinsky & Margolis, 2006), and crisis management (Ucelli, 2002). Smith and Frymier (2006) found that more challenging practice sessions (e.g., larger audiences) ultimately lead to better performance.

Initial Engagement

There are many ways to initiate a request. Since most individuals need to get comfortable before asking for a favor, it is often a good idea to begin with some non-business communication. This involves exchanging greetings, calling the other party by his/her name, discussing non-threatening and non-business topics (the weather, travels).

Offering a genuine compliment can also make both parties more relaxed, smoothing the transition to one's request (Cialdini, 1993).

Once an individual feels comfortable with the other party, there are several approaches that might be enacted. One of these approaches involves using the principle of reciprocal behavior. Most of us are scripted to return favors: If you do something for me, I feel obliged to do something for you (McGinn, Thompson & Bazerman, 2003; Molm, Collett & Schaefer, 2007). Therefore, to increase the ease and success of asking for what one wants, first find some way to help the other party (e.g., offering a gift or service). Then, this individual will be more likely to want to return the favor when one's request is made.

Rather than actually asking for a favor, some individuals will raise a topic or issue in hopes that the other party will recognize the context or intent and take the lead. For example, rather than directly asking for a newspaper on an airplane, a passenger might say "Oh, I see you have newspapers," hoping that the stewardess will offer one. An indirect approach creates less dissonance, since the negotiator can plausibly deny having volunteered a request (Festinger & Carlsmith, 1959).

By asking on behalf of someone else, a negotiator also can limit potential dissonance: If the request is denied, the source of the counter-normative proposal is presumed to be a third party rather than the negotiator (who is merely acting as an agent) (Rubin & Sander, 1988). As previously noted, women in particular have been found to be

more assertive when acting on someone else's behalf than when asking for themselves (Bowler, et al., 2005).

Another approach to initiating a request is to present the other party with a problem, implicitly asking for his/her advice or assistance. For example, one might begin by saying "Can you help me?," and then explain the problem or predicament. This places one's counterpart in the role of problem-solver and, ultimately, the counterpart will end up implementing his/her own solution (which increases the probability of follow-through).

A similar problem-solving approach involves asking one's counterpart to help choose between two options. Following a counterpart's recommendation to go with Option B, it is more difficult for this person to deny a request to pay less than the sticker price when one discovers that he/she only has funds sufficient to pay 90% of that price.

Most of these approaches may not require an individual to actually ask for a favor. If and when it comes down to actually initiating a request, there are several techniques that can help. As a way of easing into a difficult question or statement, Rackham (2003) recommends that individuals begin by labeling their behavior. For example, rather than simply asking a question, Rackham suggests that a negotiator begin by labeling or signaling the behavior that is about to follow: "Can I ask you a question?" This shows respect for the other party, and gets him or her to say "yes" to something right away. In his research, Rackham found that expert negotiators were five times as likely as average negotiators to label their behaviors.

Getting the other party to say yes to something is important for several reasons, not the least of which is the positive encouragement it gives the initiator. Ultimately, one wants to do whatever possible to get the other party to say yes to one's particular request before the other party says no. The reason is simple: It takes more information to change a decision than to make it initially (Gibson & Nicol, 1964; Pruitt, 1961). So once the other party says no, one will have to work much harder to change a counterpart's mind.

Of course, there are ways of asking a question that will almost certainly ensure a negative response. For example, the questions "You wouldn't want to ... ?" or "I don't suppose you would consider ..." beg for the other party to answer in the negative. They are almost self-fulfilling prophecies, and as a rule should be avoided.

Physiological factors (e.g., shaking, fatigue, perspiration) can be particularly debilitating for many negotiators, and challenging to overcome. Some negotiators will attempt to manage their symptoms through anxiety suppressants or other medications, which always carry the danger of dependence. Since many physiological problems are amplified by lack of experience, a better approach might be to concentrate first on other ways of bolstering self-efficacy (experience, vicarious learning, social persuasions).

Alternatively, one might attempt to limit the exposure of shaking, perspiration, etc. through the choice of a medium of lower information richness. For example, a negotiator can disguise some physiological factors by using a medium such as the telephone, and hide still more through correspondence (e.g., electronic mail). These media, however, will likely

limit a negotiator's ability to communicate persuasive emotion, and give the other party more control over the pace and duration of the encounter.

Finally, some individuals will find comfort in having a trusted and experienced colleague present during early practice sessions or important negotiations. In the case of the former, the colleague can provide subsequent support and guidance, while in the case of important negotiations this colleague can serve as a backup negotiator if the exchange gets particularly challenging or contentious.

Dealing with “No”

One of the great challenges of negotiation is dealing with rejection. When the other party says “No” we often have an emotional reaction (Fisher & Shapiro, 2005; Ury, 1991). In such cases, the limbic system will override the cerebrum, limiting our ability to think of an effective next step (Morse, 2006).

If a negotiator has planned for the possibility of a negative response, it generally will be easier to deal with a counterpart's “No.” And if the negotiator has exaggerated his/her initial request, then there will likely be an acceptable counterproposal on which to fall back. As noted, this is a standard and generally accepted tactic for optimizing one's outcome (Dees & Cramton, 1991).

In either case, the negotiator will want to understand the reasons behind the response. Asking some form of “Why?” (e.g., “I'm not sure that I understand your concerns”) or simply being silent can produce additional insights. By repeating or

paraphrasing what the other party offers as issues or concerns, the negotiator demonstrates interest, ensures understanding, and gets the other party to explicitly say something affirmative (e.g., “Yes, that’s what I said”). Once again, this “yes” becomes the first in a series of affirmations that can lead to acceding to one’s request (Ury, 1991).

Understanding the other party’s concerns or issues also might lead to a modification of one’s request, a modification that both parties can accept. For example, a supplier who rejects a buyer’s request that he/she deliver products by the end of the week may be open to having the buyer handle the pickup. This solution can only be identified if the buyer asks “Why?,” if the supplier reveals that the product is available but deliver trucks are not, and if the buyer is able to keep his/her emotions from interfering with his/her ability to move beyond “No.”

If the negotiator is caught completely by surprise (e.g., due to the nature of a counterpart’s response), he/she might ask for a break or timeout to collect his/her thoughts. Keep in mind that one’s counterpart also has scripts, so when they say “No” they expect you to respond in a particular manner (get angry, give up, etc.). By surprising counterparts with a response that they did not expect, one can sometimes change the tenor and direction of the negotiation (e.g., “I know exactly where you are coming from. My dad had a business like yours, and he also received requests of this type”).

Sometimes it is easier for a colleague or co-negotiator to introduce a creative response to a negative reply. In most cases this individual will not have had the same

emotional reaction to hearing “No” (as it was a response to your request, not your colleague’s request), and therefore will not have to contend with the limbic system overriding his/her cerebrum. The more experienced this colleague or co-negotiator, the better.

Conclusion

For many individuals, asking is one of the most difficult aspects of negotiation. Since it is both a voluntary and public act in many cases, “asking” can bring on considerable angst, even if the outcome is favorable. Unfortunately, asking is one of the first things a negotiator must do if he/she hopes to get something that is needed or desired.

The first step in managing one’s inability to ask for what he/she wants in a negotiation is to understand when this behavior occurs. Does it occur in virtually all situations? Or is it most likely to occur with certain individuals or in certain situations? For individuals who are having difficulty asking for what they want in most situations, the root cause is most likely personality traits (e.g., socialization, self-efficacy). Situational reluctance may have more to do with an inherent realization that such actions carry undue risk due to the lack of importance, available alternatives, venue, etc., and in this case the risk is not worth the potential benefit.

In seeking to master the techniques described above, an individual might consider practicing first in an environment where asking is much more common and accepted (Volkema & Fleury, 2002; Weiss, 1994). This could be another country or region, where

virtually everyone is emboldened to ask for what they want, or an industry or market where asking is more the norm (e.g., automobile buying, classified ads, yard sales). In the process, one can gain more experience and confidence in the use of various techniques.

Observing the skilled behavior of others, particularly in more challenging situations, also can help create the kinds of cognitive scripts that will guide an individual through his or her own negotiations (Nadler, Thompson & Van Boven, 2003). This type of training is common in many different venues, from sales to mediation: The trainee will first observe the behavior of skilled others, and then be assisted by a skilled salesperson or mediator when given the opportunity to take the lead.

The good news is that negotiation is a skill, and skills can be acquired through practice (Ericsson, Prietula & Cokely, 2007). And there are countless negotiations occurring daily in one's personal life where this practice can take place. By beginning with more benign situations, an individual can gain the experience and confidence to approach more challenging negotiations.

References

- Babcock, L., & Laschever, S. (2003). Women don't ask: Negotiation and the gender divide. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Bandura, A. (2001). Social cognitive theory: An agentic perspective. Annual Review of Psychology, 52, 1-26.
- Blodgett, J., Hill, D., & Bakin, A. (2006). Cross-cultural complaining behavior? An alternative explanation. Journal of Consumer Satisfaction, Dissatisfaction and Complaining Behavior, 19, 103-117.
- Bluen, S.D., & Jubiler-Lurie, V.G. (1990). Some consequences of labor-management negotiations:

Laboratory and field studies. Journal of Organizational Behavior, 11 (2), 105-118.
- Bowles, H.R., Babcock, L., & McGinn, K.L. (2005). Constraints and triggers: Situational mechanics

of gender in negotiation. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 89 (6), 951-965.
- Brett, J.F., Pinkley, R.L., & Jackofsky, E.F. (1996). Alternatives to having BATNA in dyadic

negotiation: The influence of goals, self-efficacy, and alternatives on negotiated outcomes.

International Journal of Conflict Management, 7 (2), 121-138.

- Bruner, G.C., & Pomazal, R.J. (1988). Problem recognition: The crucial first stage of the consumer decision process. The Journal of Services Marketing, 2(3), 43-53.
- Buelens, M., Van Poucke, D. (2004). Determinants of a negotiator's initial opening offer. Journal of Business and Psychology, 19 (1), 23-35.
- Cares, J., & Miskel, J. (2007). Take your third move first. Harvard Business Review, 85 (3), 20-21.
- Chang, M.K. (1998). Predicting unethical behavior: A comparison of the theory of reasoned action on the theory of planned change. Journal of Business Ethics, 17 (16), 1825-1834.
- Cialdini, R.B. (1993). Influence: The psychology of Persuasion. New York: Quill.
- Cohen, H. (1980). You can negotiate anything. Secaucus, NJ: Lyle Stuart.
- Cowan, D.A. (1986). Developing a process model of problem formulation. Academy of Management Review, 11(4), 763-776.
- D'Aveni, R.A. (2002). Competitive pressure systems: Mapping and managing multimarket contact. Sloan Management Review, 44 (1), 39-49.
- Davidson, W., & Kline, S. (1999). Ace your presentations. Journal of Accountancy, 187 (3), 61-63.
- de Dreu, C.K.W. (2003). Time pressure and closing of the mind in negotiation.

- Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes, 91 (2), 280-295.
- Dees, J.G., & Cramton, P.C. (1991). Shrewd bargaining on the moral frontier: Toward a theory of morality in practice. Business Ethics Quarterly, 1 (2), 135-167.
- Dijksterhuis, A. (2004). Think different: The merits of unconscious thought in preference development and decision making. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 87(5), 586-598.
- Ericsson, K.A., Prietula, M.J., & Cokely, E.T. (2007). The making of an expert. Harvard Business Review, 85, 114-121.
- Festinger, L., & Carlsmith, J.M. (1959). Cognitive consequences of forced compliance. Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology, 58, 203-210.
- Fisher, R., & Shapiro, D. (2005). Beyond reason: Using emotion as you negotiate. New York: Viking/Penguin.
- Fisher, R., Ury, W., & Patton, B. (1991). Getting to yes. New York: Penguin.
- Fowler, J.H., & Layer, M. (2008). A tournament of party decision rules. Journal of Conflict Resolution, 52 (1), 68-92.
- Gibson, R.S., & Nicol, E.H. (1964). The modification of decisions made in a changing environment. USAF-ESD-TR-No. 64-657.

Gist, M.E., Stevens, C.K., & Bavetta, A.G. (1991). Effects of self-efficacy and post-training

intervention on the acquisition and maintenance of complex interpersonal skills.

Personnel Psychology, 44 (4), 837-861.

Greenhalgh, L. (2001). Managing strategic relationships: The key to business success.

New York: Free Press.

Hofstede, G.H. (1997). Cultures and organizations: Software of the mind. New York:

McGraw-Hill.

Huppertz, J.H. (2003). An effort model of first-stage complaining behavior. Journal of

Consumer Satisfaction, Dissatisfaction and Complaining Behavior, 16 (2),

132-144.

Kim, M., & Hunter, J.E. (1993). Relationships among attitudes, behavioral intentions, and

behavior: A meta-analysis of past research, part 2. Communication Research, 20

(3), 331-364.

Kim, P.H., & Fragale, A.R. (2005). Choosing the path to bargaining power: An empirical

comparison of BATNA and contributions in negotiation. Journal of Applied

Psychology,

90 (2), 373-381.

Lewicki, R.J., Barry, B., & Saunders, D.M. (2007). Essentials of negotiation. Boston,

MA:

McGraw-Hill/Irwin.

London, M., Larsen, H.H., & Thisted, L.N. (1999). Relationships between feedback and self-

development. Group & Organization Management, 24 (1), 5-27.

Liu, N.F., & Littlewood, W. (1997). Why do many students appear reluctant to participate in classroom learning discourse? System, 25 (3), 371-384.

Marsland, S., & Beer, M. (1983). The evolution of Japanese management: Lessons for U.S. managers. Organizational Dynamics, 11 (3), 49-67.

McGinn, K.L., Thompson, L., & Bazerman, M.H. (2003). Dyadic processes of disclosure and

reciprocity in bargaining with communication. Journal of Behavior Decision

Making, 16

(1), 17-34.

Metcalfe, B.D. (2006). Exploring cultural dimensions of gender and management in the Middle East. Thunderbird International Business Review, 48 (1), 93-108.

Mintzberg, H. (1973). The nature of managerial work. New York: Harper & Row.

Molinsky, A., & Margolis, J. (2006). The emotional tightrope of downsizing: Hidden challenges for leaders and their organizations. Organizational Dynamics, 35 (2),

145-159.

Molm, L.D., Collett, J.L., & Schaefer, D.R. (2007). Building solidarity through generalized

exchange: A theory of reciprocity. The American Journal of Sociology, 113 (1),

205-242.

Morse, G. (2006). Decisions and desire. Harvard Business Review, 84 (1), 42, 44-51, 132.

Nadler, J., Thompson, L., and Van Boven, L. 2003. Learning negotiation skills: Four models of

knowledge creation and transfer. Management Science, 49 (4): 529-540.

O'Connor, K.M., & Adams, A.A. (1999). What novices think about negotiation: A content analysis of scripts. Negotiation Journal, 15 (2), 135-147.

Oetzel, J.G., & Ting-Toomey, S. (2003). Face concerns in interpersonal conflict: A cross-cultural empirical test of face negotiation theory. Communication Research, 30 (6), 599-624.

Pruitt, D.G. (1961). Informational requirements in making decisions. The American Journal of Psychology, 74, 433-439.

Rackham, N. (2003). The behavior of successful negotiators. In R.J. Lewicki, D.M. Saunders, J.W. Minton, & B.Barry (Eds.) Negotiation (pp. 169-181). New York: McGraw Hill/Irwin.

Rubin, J.Z., & Sander, F.E.A. (1988). When should we use agents? Direct vs. representative negotiation. Negotiation Journal, 4 (4), 395-401.

Schuster, C., & Copeland, M. (1996). Global business: Planning for sales and negotiation.

- Fort Worth, Texas: Dryden Press.
- Shell, G.R. (2001). Bargaining styles and negotiation: The Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument in negotiation training. Negotiation Journal, 17 (2), 155-174.
- Smith, T.E., & Frymier, A.B. (2006). Get “real”: Does practicing speeches before an audience improve performance? Communication Quarterly, 54 (1), 111-126.
- Steel, P., & Konig, C.J. (2006). Integrating theories of motivation. Academy of Management Review, 31 (4), 889-913.
- Thompson, J.A. (2005). Proactive personality and job performance: A social capital perspective. Journal of Applied Psychology, 90 (5), 1011-1017.
- Ucelli, L. (2002). The CEO’s “how to” guide to crisis management. Strategy & Leadership, 30 (2), 21-24.
- Ury, W. (1991). Getting past no: Negotiating with difficult people. New York: Bantam.
- Volkema, R.J. (1999). The negotiation toolkit: How to get exactly what you want in any business or personal situation. New York: Amacom.
- Volkema, R.J. (2006). Leverage: How to get it and how to keep it in any negotiation. New York: Amacom.
- Volkema, R.J., & Fleury, M.T.L. (2002). Alternative negotiating conditions and the choice of negotiation tactics: A cross-cultural comparison. Journal of Business Ethics, 36, 381-398.
- Walters, A.E., Stuhlmacher, A.F., & Meyer, L.L. (1998). Gender and negotiator

competitiveness: A meta-analysis. Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes, 76, 1-29.

Washburn, S.A. (1992). Daniel in the lion's den: Selling to groups. Journal of Management

Consulting, 7 (1), 9-19.

Weiss, S.E. (1994). Negotiating with "Romans" – Part 1. Sloan Management Review, 35 (2), 51-61.

Wheeler, M. (2004). Anxious moments: Openings in negotiation. Negotiation Journal, 20 (2), 153-169.

Wu, J., & Laws, D. (2003). Trust and other-anxiety in negotiations: Dynamics across boundaries

of self and culture. Negotiation Journal, 19 (4), 329-367.

Table 1

Techniques for Overcoming Initiation Barriers

Source of Barrier		Techniques
Dealing With “No”		Initial Engagement
<i>Negotiator characteristics</i>		
Attitude towards asking	Practice in favorable environment	
Self-efficacy		
Personal experience	Practice/rehearse techniques	
Vicarious experience negotiator	Observe experts Employ backup negotiator	Employ backup
Social persuasions	Engage supporters/coach	
Physiological factors	Select favorable medium	Label behavior;
Ask “Why?”;		Avoid self-fulfilling
questions;	Request break;	
negotiator	Employ backup negotiator	Employ backup
<i>Situational factors</i>		
Clarity of desire	Clarify/prioritize wants; Develop contingencies	

Importance	Identify broader needs	
Time constraints	Select favorable time	
Alternatives	Develop alternatives	
Counterpart (reciprocity); reference to need/issue; agent; choices		Build rapport; Help other party Make indirect Act as a presumed Present problem or
Venue	Select equitable location; Limit presence of others	

Figure 1. Model of Negotiation Engagement.

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Negotiator Characteristics

- Attitude towards such behavior
- Self-efficacy

Situational Factors

- Clarity of desire
- Importance
- Time constraints
- Alternatives
- Counterpart
- Venue

Behavior

- Engage
- Request
- Optimize

Intentions